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PHARMACOVIGILANCE PROGRAMME IN INDIA PRESENT CIRCUMSTANCE AND ITS PERSPECTIVES

Purushothama Reddy K^{1*}, Dr. Rajesh Asija², Dr. M. Purushothaman³, Dr. S. Arshiya Banu⁴

¹Rao's College of Pharmacy, Nellore, A.P – 524 320.

²Sunrise Pharmacy College, Sunrise University, Alwar, Rajasthan, India.

³Scient Institute of Pharmacy, Ibrahimpatnam, R. R. District – 501 506, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

⁴Rami Reddy Memorial College of Pharmacy, Kadapa, A.P – 516003.

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ABSTRACT

Adverse drug reaction (ADR) is defined as any response to a drug which is harmful and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function. An increased understanding of the prevalence and nature of ADRs, as well as recognition of patients perspectives on quality of life, would enable us as a profession to identify and target specific areas for vigorous pharmaceutical care. It is important to identify the risks for ADRs as they are life threatening, henceforth the common drugs causing ADRs, their therapeutic class, demographic data of patients suffered from ADRs and concomitant medications used should be known. Also, ADR specific data such as type of reaction, system affected and probable causes will be of great help to minimize the ADRs. The process of defining and concluding about ADRs should be continuous and ongoing to keep a record of newly marketed drugs and medicinal products. More over strict drug analyzing, clinical data and in vivo study is also required if feasible. This article focuses on the adverse reaction and its assessment methods.

Corresponding author

Purushothama Reddy. K

Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice,

Rao's College of Pharmacy, Nellore, A.P – 524 320.

91+ 9618266403.

reddypharma6@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

The safety concern of drug is now becoming the area of priority. The thalidomide tragedy of 1960's opened the eyes of drug regulators as well as other concern bodies to establish a way to ensure drug safety; previously the issues were in shadow. After the initiation of the Programme for International Drug Monitoring by World Health Organization (WHO) in 1968, the drug safety issues were globalized, strengthened and systematized. Years after the start of the program, India launched a Pharmacovigilance program of India (PvPi) in 2010. The main aim of this program is to give advance patient care and safety in relation to the use of medicines promising the rational and effective treatment by safeguarding the public health.¹

Pharmacovigilance (abbreviated PV or PhV The etymological roots are: *pharmakon* (Greek), “drug;” and *vigilare* (Latin), “to keep awake or alert, to keep watch.”) is the monitoring of drugs with a view to identify new information about hazards associated with products and to prevent harm to the patient. Whereas ADR, is the response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used for the prophylaxis, diagnosis or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function.² ADRs are the common clinical problem which requires minimization to reduce the economic burden of the country.

INDIAN SCENARIO

The origin of pharmacovigilance in India was started in 1986, when a formal ADR monitoring system consisting of 12 regional centers, each covering a population of 50 million, was proposed for India.³ However, nothing much happened until a decade later in 1997, India joined the WHO ADR Monitoring Programme built in Uppsala, Sweden. This attempt was unsuccessful and hence, from 1 January 2005, the WHO-sponsored and World Bank-funded National Pharmacovigilance Program for India which was further made operational.⁴ The Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI) was initiated by the Government of India in July 2010 with AIIMS, New Delhi as National Coordinating Center (NCC) for monitoring ADR's in the country for safeguarding public health by assuring the safety of medicinal products.

The NCC was shifted from AIIMS, New Delhi to IPC, Ghaziabad on 15th April 2011. Before the registration and marketing of medicine in the country, its safety and efficacy experience is monitored primarily on the use of the medicine in clinical trials. These trials also detect adverse reactions but some of the important reactions, those which take a long time to develop, or those, which occur rarely, may not be detected in the clinical trials. In addition, the controlled conditions under which medicines are used in clinical trials do not necessarily reflect the way they will be used in practice. For a medicine to be considered safe, its expected benefits should be greater than any associated risks of harmful reactions. So in order to gain a comprehensive safety profile of medicinal products, a continuous post-marketing monitoring system is essential. PvPI provides such a system to collate the data and use the inferences to recommend regulatory interventions, besides communicating risks to healthcare professionals and the public. (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Communicational organization of pharmacovigilance program of India (PvPI).

Nowadays medical Colleges and hospitals have become the cornerstone of the PvPI. They act as Adverse drug Monitoring Centers (AMCs) which are responsible for collecting the Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) and performing the follow up to obtain necessary supplementary detailed information for scientific evaluation of the cases.⁵ Currently, 150 ADR Monitoring centers (including Government and Non-government) are established under PvPI, till August 2015. In addition to that other Special centers like 20 ART (Anti-Retroviral Therapy) and 17 RNTCP (Revised National Tuberculosis Program) centers also recognized for spontaneous reporting of adverse events.⁶

Institute of Medical Sciences (IMS), Banaras Hindu University (BHU), Varanasi, is one of the recognized ADR Monitoring center (AMC) of PvPI, under Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. The PvPI unit of IMS-BHU constitutes the Head of the Department of Pharmacology as coordinator, one member (Assistant Professor level) of various clinical departments and one Technical Associate deputed by National Coordination Centre (NCC-PvPI). The technical Associate is responsible for collecting ICSRs (individual case safety report) and ensuring proper follow up. All the evaluated and signed ADR reports were entered into the VigiFlow (online software). This center also works as Regional Pharmacovigilance Centre where all government and private primary health centers (PHCs) and community health centers (CHCs) can submit their ADR reports.

In the population, there is a popular misconception that natural means safe and remedies of natural origin are harmless and are devoid of ADR. But, "Charka Samheta", classical book of Ayurveda describes that ADR occurs when herbal medicines are used or prepared inappropriately.⁷ To put pharmacovigilance for Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani (ASU) drugs in proper place in India, National Pharmacovigilance Centre for ASU drugs under the control of Department of AYUSH was introduced which is highly essential which would monitor the program centrally. AYUSH aims to provide ADR data as per WHO guidelines, most of the ADR linked with herbs and herbal products are because of poor quality or improper usage. Various drugs of herbal, mineral, metallic, animal and other origins available in the country.⁸ India is a vast country and there is a surfeit of drug brands-more than 6,000 licensed drug manufacturers and over 60,000 branded formulations.

India is one of the largest producers of pharmaceuticals in the world and is also emerging as a hub for clinical trials. Many new drugs are being introduced in the country, so there is an immense need to improve the pharmacovigilance system to protect the Indian population from potential harm that may be caused due to new drugs or by the previous drugs.⁹ The key area where pharmacovigilance incorporated is National Drug Policy. To ensure the safety and rational use of the drug, most of the countries stepped forward for the formation of drug regulatory bodies with dedicated pharmacovigilance program to monitor and assess the ADR and communicate findings to relevant stakeholders.¹⁰ Pharmacovigilance is a relatively new and small science which plays an integral part. It is well-established academic specialism through which current curricula in training programs of professions such as clinical medicines, clinical pharmacy, clinical pharmacology or medical biology covers all the skills needed in pharmacovigilance.¹¹

There is a possibility of ADRs with any class of drug. However, it was mostly observed in antibiotics and antitumor agents classes of drugs which are responsible in causing 16% and 15% of all cases of ADR.¹² ADRs are becoming most troublesome, hence there is signal is introduced. It is a potential and established indicator of new ADR. The signal is referred to as any new possible causal link between a suspected ADR and drug, which is previously unknown or incompletely documented.¹³ In recent years, many Indian companies are making investments in research and development area to enhance their capacity to develop and market a new drug with their own research efforts. Ultimately, India is becoming a new hub for clinical research activities due to its large population, high enrollment rate, and low cost. Pharmacovigilance being a robust system protects the patients from unnecessary harm by identifying previously unrecognized drug hazard, elucidating pre-disposing factors and quantifying risk in relation to benefits.¹⁴

CONCLUSION

Pharmacovigilance is the robust system which ensures the safety of drug product. It minimizes the rate of ADRs and also helps in reducing the economic burden of the country by safeguarding the public health. PvPI is one of the requisite steps taken by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India for ensuring safe and rational use of medicines. No medicinal product is completely devoid of risk and a continuous monitoring of these products is required to ensure the patient safety. Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission as National Coordination center for PvPI with all their stakeholders performing prominently in achieving its goal through their mission and objectives.

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